

The Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Sustainable Development

Country Report of Ecuador

Published in 2025 by the Ibero-American Sports Council (Consejo Iberoamericano del Deporte, CID) in collaboration with the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO).

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15126293

© Consejo Iberoamericano del Deporte, 2025

The designations employed and the presentation of material throughout this publication do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of CID or UNESCO concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. The ideas and opinions expressed in this publication are those of the authors and are not necessarily those of CID or UNESCO and do not commit the Organizations.

International Consultant:
Prof. Alfonso Jiménez Gutiérrez
PhD, CSCS, NSCA-CPT, FLF

Cover photo:
Omri D. Cohen

This document has been prepared by:
Dr. Domingo F. Hernández-Angeles^{b,d}
Dr. Daniela Hernández^{b,d}
Dr. Robert Bauer^{a,d,*}
Dr. Raúl Sánchez-García^{a,d}
Dr. Silvia González^{c,d}
Dr. Inés Nieto^{a,d}
Dr. Xián Mayo^{a,d}
Dr. Alfonso Jiménez^{a,d}

^a Research Centre in Sports Science, King Juan Carlos University, Madrid, Spain

^b UNESCO

^c District Institute of Recreation and Sports, Bogota, Colombia

^d Ibero-American Sports Council

* Correspondence:
Robert Bauer
robert.bauer@urjc.es

This Country Report is the result of intense collaborative work between the Ministry of Sport of Ecuador and the international cooperation consortium comprising the Ibero-American Sports Council (CID), UNESCO, the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF), and the Research Centre in Sports Science of the King Juan Carlos University (CIDE).

The consortium especially wishes to express its gratitude to the Research and Cooperation in Physical Culture area (currently the Directorate of Cooperation and International Relations) of the Ministry of Sport of Ecuador, as well as to the Ministerial Office and the Directorate of Monitoring Plans, Programs, and Projects, whose technical team was deeply involved and committed to developing this document.

Content

Content.....	3
Introduction.....	4
I. Country Context.....	5
II. Indicator Creation Process.....	7
III. General Progress Overview.....	8
IV. Situation of Key Data Points and Indicators.....	10
Key data point 1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.....	11
Key data point 2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity.....	12
Key data point 3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.....	13
Key data point 4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.....	14
Indicator 1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity.....	15
Indicator 2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP.....	16
Indicator 3. Percentage of the population between 18 and 69 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender.....	17
Indicator 4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old.....	19
Indicator 5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education.....	20
Indicator 6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender.....	21
Indicator 7. Percentage of the national sport entity’s budget focused on gender programs.....	22
Indicator 8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity.....	23
Indicator 9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population between 18 and 69 years old.....	24
Indicator 10. Percentage of the national sport entity’s budget focused on programs for people with disabilities.....	25
Indicator 11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population.....	26
Indicator 12. Percentage of government programs from the Health, Social Development, and Talent Cabinet that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence.....	27
V. Findings and Lessons learned.....	28
VI. Recommendations and Next Steps.....	29
Conclusions.....	30
References.....	31

Introduction

By mandate of the High Authorities of Sport in Ibero-America, including Ministers, the Ibero-American Sports Council (CID), UNESCO, and the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), have developed the first common indicators to measure the impact of sport and physical activity on sustainable development in Ibero-America. More recently, the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF) and the Research Centre in Sports Science of the King Juan Carlos University have also joined the Consortium.

The Ibero-American sports indicators aim to provide countries with periodic, standardized, and comparable information on the impact of sport in the different dimensions of sustainable development, as well as the periodic evaluation of policies that allow for identifying improvement opportunities and supporting achievements and results. Additionally, the indicators seek to facilitate the measurement of the social return of sport, which ultimately promotes increased investment in sport and physical activity.

At the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, in May 2023, the creation of 12 indicators and four key data points to be implemented in the region was unanimously approved. It was also agreed to conduct a pilot of the indicators in a group of candidate countries. The countries participating in this first stage of the pilot were Chile, Costa Rica, and Ecuador.

The pilot, carried out between August 2023 and March 2024, aimed to validate the clarity, feasibility, relevance, and cost-effectiveness of the indicators, as well as to make an initial calculation of these according to the information sources available, and from this, generate a country report on its situation and a transversal document of results and lessons learned.

In this Country Report for Ecuador, the situation of the indicators and their information sources is analyzed, as well as the challenges for their generation in accordance with the country's social, cultural, and economic context. Likewise, the linkage of the indicators with sports and physical activity policies and programs and the country's long-term strategic vision is established.

The Country Report is complemented by the technical sheets of the indicators whose values were possible to calculate, and by the general manual for creating technical sheets for the indicators that could not be estimated during the pilot. The technical sheets describe in detail the main characteristics of the indicators and facilitate their correct interpretation, implementation, and scalability. They are essential for replicating their calculation and fostering discussion among experts.

Similarly, it is also recommended to consult the Pilot Results and Lessons Learned Report, which provides an overview of the progress made by the three countries participating in the pilot and presents the technical assessment of the indicators by them. The report also includes a list of lessons learned and recommendations for the next phases of the pilot and the implementation of the indicators throughout the region, as well as the challenge of having homogeneous and comparable data collection criteria among the countries.

The country report has been the result of intensive collaborative work between the Ministry of Sport of Ecuador and the international cooperation consortium formed by the CID, UNESCO, GIZ, CAF, and Rey Juan Carlos University. In particular, the Consortium wishes to express its gratitude to the Research and Cooperation in Physical Culture area (currently the Directorate of Cooperation and International Relations) of the Ministry of Sport of Ecuador, as well as to the Ministerial Office and the Directorate of Monitoring Plans, Programs, and Projects, whose technical team was very committed to the development of this document.

I. Country Context

The state of sports and physical activity in countries is closely related to their social, cultural, and economic context, as well as their visions and priority objectives outlined in strategic policies and programs. Therefore, it is important to address the country's general characteristics in these areas to better understand the progress and challenges for sports and physical activity, as well as the difficulties in implementing the Ibero-American sports indicators in the country. While one of the most important objectives of these indicators is to ensure comparability among different countries in the region, it is also essential to understand the local factors that must be considered for their implementation.

One of the most difficult years for Ecuador in terms of economy and security was 2023, making it the most violent year in its history, with an unprecedented homicide rate of 42 per 100,000 inhabitants. Socioeconomically, the Ecuadorian economy also experienced a progressive slowdown in GDP that led to stagnation forecasts for 2024. Insecurity has impacted small businesses and foreign investment, forcing companies to address new problems such as extortion and the protection of their workforce and infrastructure, in addition to their usual business operations. Furthermore, the accumulated fiscal deficit and its resulting impact on state liquidity have led to a deterioration of public services that previously, to some extent, mitigated social inequality. This economic contraction has resulted in lower consumer spending, a lack of quality job creation, and an increase in underemployment.

On the other hand, rapid and unplanned urban growth has led to a shortage of green spaces and recreational areas, making it difficult to engage in outdoor physical activities, though this varies between cities and regions. For example, cities such as Guayaquil and Daule particularly lack green spaces for mass sports activities compared to cities like Quito and Cuenca, which have numerous recreational areas and have successfully implemented bike lanes.

Despite this scenario, Ecuador remains a country passionate about sports, which continue to provide positive news, both through the achievements of its athletes and the overall enthusiasm of Ecuadorians for sports. In recent decades, Ecuador has seen a rise in athletic success in disciplines such as athletics, cycling, soccer, weightlifting, swimming, and judo, among others. This has generated a sense of hope and motivation among the population, who view sports as an opportunity for development. Due to its regional diversity, the country boasts a rich cultural variety, including Indigenous, Afro-Ecuadorian, and Mestizo traditions, each with its own forms of physical activity and traditional sports.

The Constitution of the Republic guarantees the right of individuals to recreation, sports, and leisure (Article 24). However, Ecuador faces several challenges in achieving this constitutional commitment. These include:

- Increasing equitable access to sports facilities and physical activity programs across the country, especially in rural and marginalized communities.
- Educating the population on the importance of regular physical activity and promoting healthy lifestyles in the face of rising obesity rates and related diseases.
- Investing in the development of athletic talent from an early age and providing training and competition opportunities for Ecuadorian athletes across all sports disciplines.
- Ensuring safety for physical activity by creating secure spaces for participation and preventing sports from being affected by external factors.

- Providing employment and development opportunities for the country's youth to reduce emigration and prevent their recruitment into criminal structures due to a lack of opportunities.

As of March 2024, Ecuador has decided to refocus its Development Plan for the New Ecuador 2024-2025 (National Planning Secretariat of Ecuador, 2023) on various policies aimed at promoting sports and physical activity.

Regarding high-performance sports, a policy has been established to ensure the comprehensive preparation of elite and reserve athletes to achieve competitive success. This policy is expected to be implemented through strategies such as enhancing medical and technical support for high-performance athletes and prioritizing sports and athletes with Olympic and Paralympic potential.

Regarding physical activity, Ecuador has introduced a policy to promote the responsible use of leisure time among its population through physical activity. This policy is projected to be carried out through strategies aimed at improving access to safe and inclusive public spaces for leisure, personal development, social cohesion, and mental and physical health. Additionally, plans for maintaining sports facilities and promoting universal accessibility in public spaces will be implemented.

Finally, it is important to highlight the role of the Ministry of Sports, which has been key since 2007 in generating and executing public policies related to sports, physical education, and recreation as tools for the integral development of Ecuadorians, with the participation of all stakeholders in the sports ecosystem.

In 2022, the Ministry established seven (7) strategic objectives in its Institutional Strategic Plan 2022-2025 (Ministry of Sports Ecuador, 2021b), including:

- Increasing the participation of Ecuadorian athletes in national and international competitions.
- Increasing the percentage of high-performance athletes with disabilities.
- Expanding and improving sports infrastructure at the national level.
- Reducing the prevalence of insufficient physical activity in the population.
- Reducing sedentary behavior during a typical day.
- Enhancing the timely and transparent generation of information by stakeholders in the sports sector.
- Strengthening institutional capacities.

Beyond the economic and security crisis, as well as demographic changes, Ecuador faces the ongoing challenge of fostering sports and physical activity among its citizens. This requires a coordinated effort from all institutional and societal stakeholders involved in this goal, including the Sports System (committees, national and provincial federations, neighborhood leagues, clubs), sectoral ministries, academia, local governments, non-governmental organizations, the private sector, international forums, cooperation networks, coaches, trainers, sports administrators, and athletes.

II. Indicator Creation Process

The indicator creation process, from the mandate of the XXVIII CID Assembly in the Dominican Republic for their creation to the presentation of the pilot results at the XXX Assembly in Washington, spans a two-year period of intense work between the countries in the region and the institutions that make up the Consortium responsible for their implementation.

The timeline of the indicator creation process is shown in Figure 1, highlighting the key political, technical, and operational milestones leading up to the presentation of the pilot results.

Figure 1. *Timeline of the Indicator Creation Process*

An important aspect to highlight is that the current set of 12 indicators and four key data points is the result of a broader set of 60 indicators that was used as discussion material in an extensive participatory analysis process in the region. This process included the application of an online exploratory questionnaire with the participation of 83 specialists from different fields; 18 semi-structured interviews with experts from academia, government representatives, and international organizations; two focus groups with 22 government representatives; and a preliminary validation virtual meeting in November 2022. This event involved 37 government representatives from 17 countries in the region. Additionally, technical validation was carried out by the governments of the region during the seminar: “Plan for the creation of sports indicators in sustainable development in Ibero-America,” held in Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia in March 2023.

Based on the above, the implementation of 12 indicators and four key data points was approved at the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, as well as the implementation of a pilot program of indicators in a group of applicant countries.

In this way, in June 2023, the Consortium launched a call to the CID countries to participate in the pilot study based on certain basic technical criteria and institutional commitments for the applicant countries. After analyzing the applications, the following month, the interested countries were informed that the pilot, in its first implementation phase, would include the participation of Chile, Costa Rica, and Ecuador.

III. General Progress Overview

In relation to the results for estimating the values of the indicators, Ecuador achieved a positive performance by successfully implementing all four key data points and seven out of the twelve indicators (58.3%). The summary of progress in the indicator values is presented in Table 1, highlighting some important observations in the third column, which will be addressed in more detail in the following section.

Table 1. Results of the Implementation of Key Data Points and Indicators in the Pilot

Key Data Point	Value	Observations
1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes."
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Ministry	
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes."
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes."
Indicator	Value	Context
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	0.23%	
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	No value	It is necessary to have a satellite account for its calculation.
3. Percentage of the population between 18 and 69 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender*	78.3%	Not comparable with the value of other countries
4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	11.0%	Percentage generated by GOPA
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	No value	
6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	No value	
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	No value	
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	48.6%	
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population between 18 and 69 years old*	17.0%	Not comparable with the value of other countries
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	3.3%	
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	No value	Necessary to have a survey for its calculation.
12. Percentage of government programs from the Health, Social Development, and Talent Cabinet that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence **	1.3%	Not comparable with the value of other countries

Note: * The indicator is not comparable with other countries because there are no complete data sources to verify that the same concepts and criteria for data collection and processing are applied.

** The indicator is not comparable between countries due to differences in administrative classification and government accounting systems.

IV. Situation of Key Data Points and Indicators

This section presents the status of key data values and indicators, regardless of whether it was possible to calculate their value during the pilot phase. For each data point and indicator, a brief justification or relevance for its calculation is provided, along with its basic characteristics. Subsequently, the country's position regarding the status of the indicators is presented, along with the policies or strategic actions it is undertaking or planning to implement to strengthen compliance.

The values of the data and indicators are considered preliminary, as they result from a pilot study aimed at providing more elements to enhance the accuracy of calculation methods, the validity and transparency of information sources, and, most importantly, the comparability of indicators at the regional level. At present, several indicators are not strictly comparable across countries because the information provided is not sufficiently complete to conduct a detailed analysis of their level of comparability.

Details on indicator calculations, as well as the concepts used, can be found in the technical data sheets document for the country (for indicators with assigned values) and in the general guide for the preparation of technical data sheets (for indicators without assigned values). The main information fields included in the technical data sheets are: indicator definition, justification, calculation method, unit of measurement, year, frequency, geographic coverage, information sources, and concepts used, among others.

Key data point I. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.

Key data point with value

To support the design of sports and physical activity policies and programs with evidence, it is essential to have representative, reliable, and periodic data. A national survey on sports participation and physical activity, disaggregated by gender and age groups, is the first step in building basic indicators in this field, such as the percentage of the population that is sufficiently physically active and the existing gaps by gender or age group.

In Ecuador, the availability of data on whether there is a national survey conducted within the last five years on sports participation and physical activity, disaggregated by gender and age groups, is considered partial. This is because the survey is not representative for specific population groups, including those under 18 years old, those aged 18 to 64, and those over 65 years old. Additionally, the survey's methodological design, microdata, and basic tabulations are not directly available to the public.

Table 2. *Basic features of the key data point*

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	2023	Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (2023)

Country's Positioning

In Ecuador, reaching a political and technical consensus to establish an instrument for assessing physical inactivity levels was a significant achievement. While government initiatives have driven the development of tools and surveys to evaluate physical activity levels, it is crucial that universities and NGOs with an interest in this field also take the lead in such efforts.

The study of physical activity and sedentary behavior is not solely the responsibility of a single sectoral ministry related to sports or similar areas; it also concerns public health, education, human talent development, and social progress. In the medium term, it is essential to establish a public policy model whose planning, implementation, and monitoring take a holistic approach to the issues it seeks to address, rather than an isolated institutional perspective.

Additionally, it is important to expand the scope of similar instruments to include a more comprehensive characterization of physical activity, sports consumption, and exercise habits.

Key data point 2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity

Key data point with value

The governmental rank of the national governing body of sport and physical activity determines its ability to establish regulations, design policies, implement programs, and manage resources. Therefore, it is a key data point to establish the rank of the national governing body of sport and physical activity in the country.

It is considered that the most appropriate governmental rank for the national governing body of sport and physical activity should be that of a ministry or an entity with a high degree of autonomy and powers similar to those of a ministry.

The governmental rank of the national governing body for sport and physical activity in Ecuador is that of a Ministry.

Table 3. *Basic features of key data point*

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Ministry	2024	Presidencia de la República de Ecuador (2021)

Country's Positioning

Ecuador still faces the challenge of strengthening the role of its governing body, the Ministry of Sports, within the framework of establishing a new Sports, Physical Education, and Recreation Law, which is currently under debate in the National Assembly. The goal is to enhance its institutional capacities and focus its efforts on overseeing the Sports System. From a public policy perspective, there is an urgent need for planned intersectoral coordination to prevent duplication of efforts among public entities and to ensure their alignment with other relevant stakeholders in the development of effective public policies.

Key data point 3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.

Key data point with value

"Each education system must assign the requisite place and importance to physical education, physical activity and sport in order to establish a balance and strengthen links between physical activities and other components of education. It must also ensure that quality and inclusive physical education classes are included, preferentially on a daily basis." (UNESCO, 2015a, p. 3).

Thus, there is a need for data or indicators that allow us to assess countries' commitment to promoting physical education in early childhood—a stage that, as widely documented, is critical for shaping habits and lifestyles in adulthood.

In Ecuador, physical education is a mandatory subject in primary and secondary education nationwide. However, it is not entirely independent, as it shares instructional hours with cultural and artistic education. Therefore, the key data point value is considered partial.

Table 4. Basic features of key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	2024	Ministerio de Educación de la República del Ecuador (2023)

Country's Positioning

Ecuador must continue with its policy of maintaining physical education as an independent subject in the educational curriculum at various educational levels. However, since 2023, it is no longer fully independent in the curriculum for General Basic Education at the sublevels of Preparatory Basic (First grade), Elementary (Second, Third, and Fourth grade), and Middle Basic (Fifth, Sixth, and Seventh grade), as it shares five (5) hours per week with "Cultural and Artistic Education." Therefore, it is only independent for the higher basic sublevel (Eighth, Ninth, and Tenth grades; with an average age of 12 to 15 years) and for high school (15-17 years). Despite these changes, it remains a subject that continues to be highlighted in the publication of educational curricula.

Key data point 4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.

Key data point with value

Legal frameworks are of special relevance because they express fundamental principles and rights of individuals, as well as the priorities and scope of objectives, strategies, and programs. This highlights the importance of having data on the existence of legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.

To establish the existence of such legal frameworks and to confirm their effective application, it is necessary to present evidence that the legal instruments have been used to design policies, programs, or actions with concrete results to promote, enforce, and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.

In Ecuador, there are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity. However, for this report, no evidence was provided regarding their application, so the key data point value is considered partial.

Table 5. Basic features of the key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Partially	2024	Ministerio del Deporte de la República del Ecuador, Ministerio de la Mujer y Derechos Humanos, Consejo Nacional para la Igualdad de Discapacidades, Consejo Nacional para la Igualdad de Género y ONU Mujeres (2023).

Country's Positioning

Evaluating the proper application of the available legal instruments to promote and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity will largely depend on the existence of reports regarding actual follow-up on this issue in the future, and on how entities organize at the intersectoral level to highlight progress in implementing regulations such as the "Protocol for Action in Cases of Gender-Based Violence in the Sports System of Ecuador," among others.

Indicator I. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity

Indicator with value

The allocation of the budget to sports and physical activity is an objective measure of the importance assigned to the sector within public investment priorities, and at the same time, it serves as a concrete reference for the scope of policies in terms of available resources.

A limitation of the indicator is that it does not account for the budget allocated to sports and physical activity for government offices outside the national governing entity in this area. Therefore, it is desirable that in the future, a broader indicator be developed to more accurately capture the amount of public resources allocated to the sector.

The percentage of Ecuador's public budget allocated to the Ministry of Sports, the national governing entity for sports and physical activity, was 0.23% in 2023, amounting to 73,905,635.76 US dollars.

Table 6. Basic features of the indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	0.23% equivalent to 73,905,635.76 USD	2023	Ministerio del Deporte de la República del Ecuador (2022)

Country's Positioning

The main difficulty lies in reaching a consensus and defining what constitutes investment in sports and physical activity, as a sectoral ministry does not necessarily concentrate the full potential of public investment made by a country in sports. For example, this investment may also be included in the budgets of decentralized autonomous governments.

On the other hand, for the purposes of the methodology used in this exercise, the main challenge was identifying information sources that allow for viewing public investment budgets with an annual evolution perspective. This way, the data can reflect as much as possible the budget approved by the National Assembly and the budget planned and executed during the year.

Indicator 2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP

Indicator without value

Sports and physical activity have a significant impact on multiple sectors and economic activities. However, due to the lack of measurements or information records, this impact has not been adequately visualized or valued. Therefore, having statistics on the contribution of sports and physical activity to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) would help highlight their impact, understand their relationship with other sectors or economic activities, and also support the design of policies and programs.

Despite its importance, obtaining this indicator poses considerable challenges for countries due to the technical complexity of its calculation and the financial needs to create its information sources. The ideal information source for the indicator is a satellite account for sports and physical activity. A satellite account is a national accounting tool that systematically and comprehensively records all transactions conducted by the economic agents of a country related to a sector or activity, in this case, sports and physical activity.

Typically, a satellite account takes three to four years from its conception to execution and the generation of results. Therefore, it was not the objective of the pilot to calculate this indicator, but rather for countries to become familiar with the scope and requirements of a satellite account.

Without the need for a satellite account, approximations of the contribution of sports and physical activity to GDP are possible. However, the data is not as precise or disaggregated, and it requires making multiple assumptions. For example, for all the countries in the European Union, data is available on the contribution of sports and physical activity to GDP, but less than half of the countries have a satellite account for sports.

Table 7. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

Obtaining this indicator for Ecuador was not feasible as it depended on the conceptualization of economic activities and the availability of official sources. This indicator would require joint work at the interinstitutional level, working groups, and, above all, political leadership to maintain its work agenda in the medium term. In this sense, it is difficult to foresee whether the methodology proposed in this exercise would align with the divergent technical criteria from other entities, in case a sectoral agenda had been established for its quantification. Nevertheless, it is important to achieve a global monetary value of all goods and services related to sports and physical activity. The Ministry will monitor the results of the pilot projects from other countries in order to propose methodologies when intersectoral alignment initiatives related to the economics of sports are called.

Indicator 3. Percentage of the population between 18 and 69 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender

Indicator with value

Regular physical activity is one of the most important mechanisms for the prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, and several types of cancer. Physical activity is also beneficial for mental health, as it prevents cognitive decline and symptoms of depression and anxiety (WHO, 2020). Therefore, it is crucial to have indicators on the percentages of the population that are sufficiently physically active.

Simultaneously, given the different needs of individuals and the existing inequalities among them, it is important to break down the indicators by age, sex or gender, ethnic origin, or socioeconomic status, among other factors. This allows for the visibility of inequalities and inclusion challenges for sports and physical activity policies.

It is important to note that the value of this indicator is not comparable between countries, although this is how it is expected to be in the future. The causes of the differences between the pilot countries are not very clear because none of them provided complete methodology, questionnaires, coding manuals, and microdata from the source surveys. It is possible that, in practice, countries are using different ways of accounting for the time spent on sports and physical activity, but due to the lack of information, this cannot be confirmed. Without a doubt, the comparability of indicators between countries is one of the great areas of opportunity.

To ensure the comparability of indicators resulting from surveys, there are two possible scenarios:

The first is to apply the same survey design, methodology, and questionnaires with the same criteria for coding information. This alternative would be the most accurate but would require waiting several years for results and would also entail a significant investment of resources from all countries.

The second scenario would involve standardizing the statistical information, but for this, more complete sources of information (methodologies, questionnaires, microdata, etc.) and more specialized technical teams from the countries would be necessary. This scenario seems more feasible, but given the technical work required, it is recommended that countries seek help from a local university specialized in the subject.

Table 8. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the population between 18 and 69 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	78.3%	2022	Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (INEC) de la República de Ecuador (2023)

Country's Positioning

The main difficulty in obtaining this indicator was the lack of availability of official published information on population statistics disaggregated by sex and age, related to the National Population and Housing Census of 2023, in disaggregated table formats. Therefore, to report the indicator, additional processing was required for the available databases on the National Institute of Statistics and Census (INEC) website. To facilitate future calculations, the Ministry of Sport will request that the information resulting from the Physical Activity and Sedentary Behavior Module of the National Employment, Unemployment, and Underemployment Survey be published in disaggregated database formats and tables, rather than just in a visualizer format.

Another difficulty encountered for the calculation of the indicator was the lack of disaggregated information regarding the projected population for 2022, given the large number of years between the 2010 Census and the 2023 one. Similarly, the Ministry of Sport will recommend to the INEC the issuance of reports that quantify the population in the years prior to the 2023 census based on disaggregated variables, to have comparable data for this exercise or similar initiatives.

Indicator 4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old

Indicator with value

According to the WHO (2022), "Physical inactivity is one of the leading risk factors for noncommunicable diseases mortality. People who are insufficiently active have a 20% to 30% increased risk of death compared to people who are sufficiently active."

Therefore, it becomes essential to have indicators on deaths related to physical inactivity that allow quantifying the magnitude of the problem for each country, and from this, implement policies to address it.

The percentage of deaths due to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old in Ecuador is 11.0%.

Table 9. Basic features of the indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	11.0%	2021	Global Observatory for Physical Activity (2021)

Country's Positioning

There are no comments regarding this indicator, as it is directly associated with the source Global Observatory for Physical Activity (GOPA, 2021), where the methodology used, assumptions, and sources of information employed are available. At the time, the Ministry of Sport suggested that this indicator may not necessarily reflect mortality from physical inactivity. The consulting team from the Consortium noted that, based on the methodology used by GOPA, there is insufficient evidence to assume that the indicator does not reflect what its name indicates, that is, the percentage of deaths due to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old.

On the other hand, considering that the factors "relative risk adjusted for all causes of mortality due to physical inactivity" and "prevalence of insufficient physical activity standardized by age" are standardized, there is not much the country can do regarding its modification in the medium term.

However, the Ministry will take it into account in future intersectoral coordination meetings, particularly with Ministries related to Health and the Social Cabinet, considering the debate on a methodology that calculates mortality due to causes related to physical activity, which could be influenced by administrative records from the Ministry of Health and death statistics.

Indicator 5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education

Indicator without value

"Physical education is the most effective means of providing all children and youth with the skills, attitudes, values, knowledge and understanding for lifelong participation in society" (UNESCO, 2015b, p. 6).

Due to the previous reasons, it is important to know the percentage of primary and secondary schools that provide the minimum number of minutes of physical education. To have a reliable indicator, it is desirable that this be the result of a school census or, if not possible, a representative survey. For Ecuador, at the moment, there is not enough information to establish the value of the indicator.

Table 10. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

The attainment of this indicator according to the proposed guidelines requires intersectoral coordination, in which a research methodology is established to determine the total number of educational institutions that do not meet the minimum required minutes of physical education. Although all educational institutions in Ecuador are obligated to comply with the current curriculum of the Ministry of Education for the different age groups, no published information is available on this matter.

Indicator 6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender

Indicator without value

The effectiveness of policies for sports and physical activity in education should ultimately be reflected in the proportion of sufficiently active students, especially at the basic education level, as this is where important lifelong habits are formed. This underscores the importance of having such an indicator. Additionally, it is crucial to break down the indicator by gender, as female students have historically faced greater setbacks compared to their male peers in various aspects of development, including sports and physical activity.

Table 11. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

The attainment of this indicator according to the proposed guidelines requires intersectoral coordination to implement a specific survey for the education sector regarding the measurement of physical activity. Although no published information is available on this matter, the survey in effect as of 2023 (the physical activity module of Enemdu) provides data on physical activity for children and adolescents aged 5 to 17 years.

Indicator 7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs

Indicator without value

In the budgets of public entities and their objectives, the political and programmatic priorities of the government are reflected, and therefore, they constitute an objective measure to assess the government's efforts to close the gender gaps in sports and physical activity.

To establish the proportion of the budget focused on gender-specific programs, it is necessary for these programs to have explicit and verifiable objectives and actions aimed at closing the gender gaps.

Table 12. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

The Ministry of Sport of Ecuador has implemented several interventions related to promoting gender gap reduction. In this regard, in February 2023, the "Protocol for Action in Cases of Gender Violence in Ecuador's Sports System" was issued, along with workshops for its implementation to raise awareness about gender equality. Additionally, during the 2023 Pan American Games, Ecuador had a higher participation of women (90) compared to men (86).

Alongside these initiatives, the Ministry could report various efforts and activities related to gender-related topics. However, regarding resource allocation, there is no established conceptualization or classification of funds provided to sports organizations based on this theme, meaning that this information is not disaggregated for financial reporting purposes. To better reflect gender-related efforts, the methodology for this indicator recommended analyzing whether it should be modified based on the number of gender-related interventions or the participation/beneficiaries of women in services implemented by the Ministry and sports organizations.

Indicator 8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity

Indicator with value

In leadership positions within public or private organizations, one of the most significant gaps between women and men is observed. This highlights the importance of monitoring the situation and progress towards gender equality in leadership roles within national entities for sports and physical activity. Based on this information, it will be possible to support better policies or affirmative actions in this area.

In Ecuador, 48.6% of leadership positions in the national sports entity (Ministry of Sport) are held by women, indicating that gender equality between men and women in this area is close to being achieved.

Table 13. Basic features of the indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	48.6%	2023	Ministerio del Deporte de la República del Ecuador (2023)

Country's Positioning

This indicator provides visibility regarding women in leadership positions within the institution. However, it is considered appropriate to expand its scope to include not only leadership positions in the national sports entity but also those in sports organizations across the country.

Indicator 9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population between 18 and 69 years old

Indicator with value

There are notable differences in the level of physical activity between women and men, particularly, "the data shows that in almost all countries, girls and women are less active than boys and men" (WHO, 2020, p. 2). In fact, it can also be observed in most countries in the region that the gender gaps increase significantly with age.

One of the most important objectives of sustainable development is to eliminate gender gaps or differences in their multiple dimensions. Therefore, it is crucial that governments and the general public have indicators that allow them to monitor their progress toward reducing or eliminating gender gaps in physical activity between men and women.

Table 14. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population between 18 and 69 years old	17.0%	2023	Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (INEC) de la República de Ecuador (2023)

Country's Positioning

This indicator was made possible by the existence of a national survey on physical activity, which disaggregates its measurement by sex. However, obtaining census data on the country's situation was challenging due to the conditions of the National Census, as described in the analysis of Indicator 3. The challenge remains to ensure that those responsible for publishing information at INEC can provide transparent tabulations by sex and age for the year 2023, as well as projections for future years and agreements on quantification scenarios for previous years; specifically, a disaggregated population projection for Ecuador between 2011 and 2022.

Indicator 10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities

Indicator with value

The Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities establishes that, in order for people with disabilities to participate on an equal footing in recreational, leisure, and sports activities, countries must adopt measures to encourage and promote the participation of people with disabilities in sports activities, ensure they have the opportunity to organize and develop sports and recreational activities, and guarantee their access to sports facilities (UN, 2008).

To put into practice what is established in the Convention, it is necessary to allocate public funds to programs aimed at enabling people with disabilities to access sports and physical activity. Similarly, it is essential to invest in data and indicators with the purpose of measuring whether this objective is being achieved.

The percentage of the Ministry of Sport of Ecuador's budget allocated to programs for people with disabilities was 3.3% in 2023, equivalent to 2,440,046.84 USD.

Table 15. Basic features of the indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	3.3% equivalent a 2,440,046.84 USD	2023	Ministerio del Deporte de la República del Ecuador (2024)

Country's Positioning

This indicator resulted from internal efforts to define which investment amounts could be considered related to disability, establishing criteria for including resources from investment projects and current expenditures. This exercise is also relevant for ongoing intersectoral alignment initiatives that require the Ministry's contribution to disability-related matters. Given that the necessary information sources are available, the Ministry is able to continue conducting this analysis using the established methodology for the year 2024.

Indicator II. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population

Indicator without value

People with disabilities are one of the population groups with the greatest delay in access to development under equal circumstances. For this reason, the way to verify whether policies or programs aimed at the population with disabilities are effectively achieving results is to observe whether their physical activity and sports gaps compared to the rest of the population are decreasing.

To achieve this, it is necessary to have representative surveys on the physical activity levels of the population with disabilities, with disaggregation by age, sex, or gender.

Table 16. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

There is no possibility of disaggregating data related to the disability sector in the national survey on physical activity. In general, it would be important to assess whether an adapted methodology is needed for this segment.

Indicator I2. Percentage of government programs from the Health, Social Development, and Talent Cabinet that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence

Indicator with value

Sports overcome geographical, social, and political barriers; connect people, communities, and countries; and in this way, promote coexistence and social and political inclusion.

Sport for development and peace is conceived as a social intervention strategy that, using games, physical activity, and sports, addresses explicit objectives of peace and development. This perspective "incorporates issues such as gender equality, the promotion of peaceful coexistence, fostering tolerance for differences, encouraging inclusive behaviors, conflict prevention, and promoting health and well-being" (GIZ, 2021).

For this reason, the relevance of generating indicators on related topics is clear, but at the same time, it presents a challenge for countries due to the technical complexity involved in designing reliable, accurate, and transparent indicators. In Ecuador, in 2023, 1.3% of government projects from the health, social development, and talent cabinet use sports as a tool for peace and coexistence.

Table 17. Basic features of the indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of government programs from the Health, Social Development, and Talent Cabinet that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	1.3%	2023	Ministerio de Deporte de Ecuador (2021a)

Country's Positioning

This indicator was derived based on the classification of government projects in the national budget of the Executive, focusing on a set of projects under the management of the Health, Social Development, and Human Talent Cabinets. It is important to note that the nature of sports-related projects is aimed at promoting physical activity, which in turn positively influences society and fosters the creation of friendship bonds. Olympic values promote solidarity, the joy of effort, social responsibility, the educational value of good example, non-discrimination, and equality. In this sense, it is difficult to disaggregate this data, as sports projects do not necessarily specify "peace and coexistence" as one of their objectives, although they do promote them. Each recreational event or competition is an effort towards this goal.

A challenge is to have a conceptual framework that allows the classification of government programs based on whether they meet the criteria of being instruments for peace and coexistence, as they are not necessarily explicit about this concept, though they may be related. Regarding the Ministry, the "Encuentro Activo para el Desarrollo" project, and in particular its initiative "Hincha de mi barrio," was a socio-sports service that during 2023 promoted values of empathy, trust, discipline, respect, and fair play among Ecuadorian children. Starting in 2024, this service will be known as "Vamos a la Cancha."

V. Findings and Lessons learned

Based on the results and observations during the execution of the pilot, the following are some of the most relevant findings and lessons learned for Ecuador:

- The implementation of the indicators requires strong political commitment from the countries and their institutions, but this commitment must be reflected in the formation of specialized, trained technical teams with the availability of time to carry out the activities required by the pilot.
- The lack of complete information sources, both for the indicators that could be calculated and for those that could not, is a serious limitation in generating representative and comparable indicators across countries in the region. Specifically, for the indicators resulting from surveys, it was not possible to have complete methodologies, questionnaires, coding manuals, and microdata. Therefore, it is not possible to establish with certainty the degree of comparability of Ecuador's indicators with those of other countries.
- The generation of indicators and the creation of their information sources require multidisciplinary and intersectoral teams to understand and operationalize concepts. From there, it is possible to have better conditions for understanding, calculating, and monitoring the indicators.
- The measurement and policy monitoring capabilities of governments can be substantially improved through partnerships with academia or specialized research centers. In addition to their benefits for knowledge generation, these partnerships would ensure continuity in the generation of information and the monitoring of indicators.
- Having reliable, periodic, and relevant information and indicators requires investment from both governments and society as a whole. Specifically, for the calculation of some indicators, it is necessary for the government to allocate budgetary resources for the creation of new representative surveys, satellite accounts, or administrative records. Similarly, investment is needed to develop capabilities for data collection, indicator creation, and evaluation and monitoring mechanisms.

On the other hand, to have a broader view of the findings and lessons learned for all the countries participating in the pilot and the international cooperation consortium, it is recommended to consult the general document of results and lessons learned, which emphasizes the challenges related to the sufficiency of information sources, the comparability of indicators between countries, and recommendations for the next phases of the pilot.

VI. Recommendations and Next Steps

With the objective of implementing all Ibero-American indicators and continue strengthening the country's measurement and information generation capabilities to design evidence-based policies, the following recommendations are made:

- Formation of an interdisciplinary and intersectoral working group (sport, health, economy, national statistics) for mapping information sources and indicators on sport and its impact on development, as well as to propose policies and technical criteria for the generation of statistical information in the field.
- In coordination with the intersectoral working group and the international cooperation consortium, establish a work plan to create the information sources for the indicators that could not be calculated during the pilot. The work plan should include work schemes and responsibilities for the different types of actors, potential sources of funding, and work schedules.
- Given the limited availability of information, even for the indicators that were successfully calculated, it is necessary to generate a work plan to make complete and detailed methodologies, questionnaires, coding manuals, and microdata from the currently available representative surveys publicly available. In addition to ensuring greater transparency, this would allow the Consortium to establish better mechanisms to standardize the information resulting from the different countries in the region.
- Design a strategy for monitoring and tracking the indicators, which, in addition to implementing the baseline for all the indicators, includes an initial follow-up report to observe the evolution of the indicators. The strategy should also include preliminary goals for the indicators.
- Establish a working mechanism with a local university for the joint development of the indicators and to build measurement capacities in the public sector related to sports and physical activity.
- Hold working meetings with experts to establish an initial set of goals for the indicators.
- Promote international cooperation mechanisms to share experiences, knowledge, and training.
- Seek partnerships with financial institutions or international investment funds focused on highlighting inclusion gaps in access to sports and the development of women, people with disabilities, indigenous populations, and people in poverty through reliable indicators and statistical information.
- Make significant investments in human resource training for the generation of indicators and monitoring and evaluation systems on the impact of sports on development.

Conclusions

The four key data points and seven of the 12 indicators were calculated, which is considered a very good performance since indicators were estimated above the forecasted levels at the beginning of the pilot. However, it is necessary to improve the accuracy and transparency of the existing information and create new sources of information to compute those indicators that could not be estimated during the pilot. Additionally, the objective of identifying challenges and opportunities for the implementation of the indicators in Ecuador and achieving their comparability with indicators from other countries in the region was met.

Given the innovative nature of the indicators, not only for the Ibero-American region but also for the world, the process for their construction and implementation should be gradual and well-documented, with spaces for technical reflection as well as for evaluating their policy implications and international cooperation.

Ecuador's experience in the pilot has been valuable in allowing the mapping of information, identifying challenges, locating opportunities, and preparing work teams for the broader implementation of the indicators in the near future. At the same time, its experience will serve as a reference for the countries that will participate in the next phases of the indicator pilot, enabling them to advance more effectively in their own indicators.

Finally, the pilot has brought together various experts in sports and physical activity from Ecuador and the region, which could mark the beginning of forming multisectoral and interdisciplinary teams required to understand and calculate the indicators. At the same time, this could translate into broader bilateral and multilateral cooperation projects, strengthening the transfer of knowledge in Ibero-America regarding measurements and indicators to support policies and achieve results in sports and sustainable development.

References

- GIZ, Agencia Alemana de Cooperación Internacional (2021): *Deporte con principios*. Disponible en: [https://www.sport-for-development.com/imglib/downloads/Country%20Collection/Columbia/Manual%20Deporte%20on%20Principios%20Versi%C3%B3n%2020\(GIZ,%202021,%20es\).pdf](https://www.sport-for-development.com/imglib/downloads/Country%20Collection/Columbia/Manual%20Deporte%20on%20Principios%20Versi%C3%B3n%2020(GIZ,%202021,%20es).pdf) [Consulta: 12 de septiembre de 2023].
- GOPA, Global Observatory for Physical Activity (2021): *2nd Physical Activity Almanac*. Disponible en: <https://indd.adobe.com/view/cb74644c-ddd9-491b-a262-1c040caad8e3> [Consulta: 14 de septiembre de 2023].
- Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos de la República de Ecuador (2023): *Módulo de Actividad Física y Comportamiento Sedentario. Encuesta Nacional de Empleo, Desempleo y Subempleo*. Disponible en: https://www.ecuadorencifras.gob.ec/documentos/web-inec/Estadisticas_Sociales/Actividad_fisica/2022/Diciembre/202212_Actividad%20Fisica.pdf [Consulta: 12 de febrero de 2024].
- Ministerio del Deporte de la República del Ecuador (2024): *Desglose de presupuesto relacionado a temáticas sobre deporte para personas con discapacidad: 2023*. Disponible en: https://www.deporte.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2024/02/Anexo_1.10_Presupuesto-Relacionado-a-Discapacidad-Ecuador-2023.pdf [Consulta: 29 de febrero de 2024].
- Ministerio del Deporte de la República del Ecuador (2023): *Distributivo de personal de la institución. Procesos gobernantes / Nivel directivo*. Página 1. Disponible en: <https://www.deporte.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2023/08/literal-b2-Distributivo-de-personal-julio-2023.pdf> [Consulta: 16 de febrero de 2024].
- Ministerio del Deporte de la República del Ecuador (2022): *Cédula presupuestaria del sistema de finanzas públicas. Información total sobre el presupuesto anual que administra la entidad*. Disponible en: <https://www.deporte.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2023/10/Literal-g-Presupuesto-de-la-Institucion.pdf> [Consulta: 29 de febrero de 2024].
- Ministerio de Deporte de Ecuador (2021a): *Encuentro Activo del Deporte Para el Desarrollo 2022-2025*. Disponible en: <https://www.asambleanacional.gob.ec/es/contenido/presupuesto-general-del-estado-2023> [Consulta: 14 de abril de 2024].
- Ministerio del Deporte Ecuador (2021b): *Plan Estratégico Institucional 2022-2025*. Disponible en: <https://www.deporte.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2022/03/PLAN-ESTRATE%CC%81GICO-MINISTERIO-DEL-DEPORTE-2022-2025.pdf> [Consulta: 14 de junio de 2024].
- Ministerio del Deporte de la República del Ecuador, Ministerio de la Mujer y Derechos Humanos, Consejo Nacional para la Igualdad de Discapacidades, Consejo Nacional para la Igualdad de Género y ONU Mujeres (2023): *Protocolo de actuación frente a casos de violencia de género en el sistema deportivo del Ecuador*. Disponible en: <https://ecuador.unwomen.org/sites/default/files/2023-04/Protocolo%20de%20Actuaci%C3%B3n%20frente%20a%20casos%20de%20violencia%20de%20g%C3%A9nero%20en%20el%20sistema%20deportivo%20ecuatoriano.pdf> [Consulta: 16 de febrero de 2024].
- Ministerio de Educación de la República del Ecuador (2023): *Acuerdo Nro. MINEDUC-MINEDUC-2023-00008-A. Plan de estudios. Artículo 7*. Disponible en: <https://educacion.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2023/03/MINEDUC-MINEDUC-2023-00008-A.pdf> [Consulta: 15 de febrero de 2024].

- OMS, Organización Mundial de la Salud (2022): *Actividad física. Datos y cifras*. Disponible en: <https://www.who.int/es/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity#:~:text=La%20OMS%20define%20la%20actividad,el%20consiguiente%20consumo%20de%20energ%C3%ADa> [Consulta: 9 de septiembre de 2023]
- OMS, Organización Mundial de la Salud (2021): *Cuestionario Mundial sobre Actividad Física (GPAQ)*. Disponible en: <https://www.who.int/es/publications/m/item/global-physical-activity-questionnaire> [Consulta: 13 de septiembre de 2023].
- OMS, Organización Mundial de la Salud (2020): *Directrices de la OMS sobre actividad física y hábitos sedentarios*. Disponible en: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/337004/9789240014817-spa.pdf> [Consulta: 10 de septiembre de 2023].
- OMS, Organización Mundial de la Salud (2019a): *Para crecer sanos, los niños tienen que pasar menos tiempo sentados y jugar más*. Disponible en: <https://www.who.int/es/news/item/24-04-2019-to-grow-up-healthy-children-need-to-sit-less-and-play-more> [Consulta: 14 de septiembre de 2023].
- OMS, Organización Mundial de la Salud (2019b): *Prevalence of insufficient physical activity among school going adolescents. Data by country*. Disponible en: <https://apps.who.int/gho/data/node.main.A893ADO?lang=en> [Consulta: 14 de septiembre de 2023].
- OMS, Organización Mundial de la Salud (2018): *Prevalence of insufficient physical activity among adults. Data by country*. Disponible en: <https://apps.who.int/gho/data/node.main.A893?lang=en> [Consulta: 14 de septiembre de 2023].
- ONU, Organización de las Naciones Unidas (2009): *Diseño de muestras para encuestas de hogares Directrices prácticas*. Disponible en: https://unstats.un.org/unsd/publication/seriesf/seriesf_98s.pdf [Consulta: 10 de septiembre de 2023].
- ONU, Organización de las Naciones Unidas (n.d.): *Convivir en paz: un proceso necesario para el desarrollo sostenible*. Disponible en: <https://www.un.org/es/observances/living-in-peace-day#:~:text=La%20Asamblea%20General%20sigue%20dando,de%20mutuo%20entendimiento%20y%20cooperaci%C3%B3n> [Consulta: 12 de septiembre de 2023]
- ONU, Organización de las Naciones Unidas (2008): *Convención sobre los derechos de las personas 37 con discapacidad*. Disponible en: <https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/enable/documents/tccconvs.pdf> [Consulta: 14 de septiembre de 2023]
- ONU Mujeres (n.d.): *Conceptos y definiciones*. Disponible en: <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/osagi/conceptsanddefinitions.htm> [Consulta: 19 de septiembre de 2023]
- OPS, Organización Panamericana de la Salud (2019): *Plan de acción mundial sobre actividad física 2018-2030. Más personas activas para un mundo sano*. Disponible en: http://0-https://iris.paho.org/bitstream/handle/10665.2/50904/9789275320600_spa.pdf [Consulta: 9 de septiembre de 2023].
- Presidencia de la República de Ecuador (2021): *Decreto presidencial. La Secretaría del Deporte se denominará Ministerio del Deporte. Artículo 1, página 2*. Disponible en: https://observatorioplanificacion.cepal.org/sites/default/files/instrument/files/Decreto_Ejecutivo_N_3.pdf [Consulta: 15 de febrero de 2024].
- Secretaría Nacional de Planificación de Ecuador (2023): *Plan de Desarrollo para el Nuevo Ecuador 2024 - 2025*. Disponible en: <https://www.planificacion.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/PND2024-2025.pdf> [Consulta: 14 de junio de 2024].

UNESCO, Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Educación, la Ciencia y la Cultura (2015a): *Carta Internacional de la Educación física, la actividad física y el deporte*. Disponible en: https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000235409_spa [Consulta: 9 de septiembre de 2023].

UNESCO, Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Educación, la Ciencia y la Cultura (2015b): *Educación Física de Calidad. Guía para los responsables políticos*. Disponible en: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000231340> [Consulta: 9 de septiembre de 2023].

UNESCO, Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Educación, la Ciencia y la Cultura y ONU Mujeres (2023): *Tackling violence against women and girls in sport. A Handbook for Policy Makers and Sport Practitioners*. Disponible en: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000385850.locale=en> [Consulta: 9 de septiembre de 2023]. [Consulta: 9 de septiembre de 2023].